

Numerical Investigation of Cold Formed Steel Plain Channel Stub Columns Subjected to Concentric and Eccentric Compressive Loading

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Abstract Cold-formed steel members are susceptible to local, distortional, global, and interactive buckling modes. The Plain channel section comprises stiffened and unstiffened elements concerning local buckling and does not undergo distortional buckling. Local buckling deformation of the section results in an effective shift in centroid, which further reduces its capacity for pin-supported stub columns compared to fixed-supported stub columns. Plain channels are used mainly as wall studs and are subject to axial compression with bending moments. These conditions require a complete understanding of elements subject to varying compressive stress distribution in local and post-local buckling behaviour. The inter-element interaction can result in the lowest ultimate strength if both stiffened and unstiffened elements undergo simultaneous local buckling. This simultaneous local buckling is demonstrated through the cross-section aspect ratio (web-to-flange ratio), which is generally omitted in the design. Cold-formed steel sections fall under slender sections, which will undergo local buckling before yielding and cannot be designed as per IS:800-2007. The Effective Width Method accounts the local buckling of the cross-section in the design through the various effective widths corresponding to compressive stress distribution in the elements. IS:801-1975 details the design guidelines for cold-formed steel members. EWM involves a tedious iterative design procedure and does not account for the inter-element interaction leading to a conservative design. Implementing the EWM is simple for the plain channel but complicated for the cross-sections having more elements. The Direct Strength Method, which includes the inter-element interactions and accounts for the gross-section properties without iteration, is simple and effective for any cross-section shape. This study examines the influence of the aspect ratio of the plain channel subject to uniaxial eccentric loading through a systematic numerical analysis and compares the results with DSM predictions. The results are summarized, and essential conclusions on the limitations of DSM are discussed.

Keywords Local Buckling, Cold-Formed Steel, Plain Channel

Introduction

Cold-formed steel has its humble beginnings in small metal components and has been in use for at least a century. The cold-forming processes result in cold-form steel members which are susceptible to any one among local, distortional, global, and coupled buckling modes. The cold-formed steel sections are generally monosymmetric open sections, due to its forming process and has less torsional resistance. Closed sections and bisymmetric sections are formed by built-up sections. Among open sections, the plain channel section finds its application as wall studs owing to the section's geometric and manufacturing simplicity. When the plain channel is designed as a stub column under pin-ended condition, it undergoes local buckling which has the potential to shift the line of action of the internal force resulting in effective shift in centroid [1–4]. This shift introduces eccentricity in loading condition which demands treating the stub column as a beam-column [5]. When plain channels are subjected to uniaxial eccentric loading it is generally observed that the shift of load position towards the supported edge resulted in the increase of ultimate load [6, 7]. Cold-form steel sections are provided with stiffeners to enhance their performance against local buckling. Stiffeners can be provided at the open section edges known as edge or flange stiffeners or lip and along the length or at web known as intermediate stiffeners or web stiffeners. A channel section with intermediate stiffeners will exhibit the highest ultimate load when compared to lipped and plain channel [8, 9]. The design of cold-form steel members is necessary to determine their capacity to carry the load by fixing desired dimensions. The Direct Strength Method (DSM) is a relatively newer approach that has gained popularity in recent years in the design of cold-formed steel structures. DSM considers the inter-element interactions [10] and considers the gross cross-section. It incorporates all important buckling modes i.e., local, distortional, global, and local-global interaction. It can be applied to accurately calculate the nominal design strength of compression members without lip or intermediate stiffeners [11]. DSM for beam-column can make use of the linear interaction equation [12, 13]. However, the current DSM design procedure specified in the codes of practice does not consider the aspect ratio of the cross-section which significantly influenced the local buckling strength of plain channel sections leading to designs that were unconservative to local buckling. To address this limitation, a modified DSM design procedure was introduced [14]. This study presents a numerical investigation of plain channel sections to understand the local buckling behaviour of beam-column with varying elemental stress distribution. The model dimensions were fixed based on the web height to flange width ratio (h/b), width to thickness ratio, and length of the models. Two different h/b ratios of 1 -to induce local buckling in the unstiffened element- and 3.05 -to induce simultaneous local buckling of both stiffened and unstiffened elements- are incorporated in this study. The size effect was taken into consideration for two different cross-sections by keeping the h/b ratio and flange width-to-thickness ratio constant. The effect of two different yield stresses of 266 MPa and 350 MPa on the ultimate load was included in the study. The eccentric load was varied along both symmetric and non-symmetric axes to mimic the stress variations among the elements as considered in the European standards. Accordingly, eight eccentric and concentric loading conditions were selected for each cross-section. Biaxial eccentricity has not been considered in this study since uniaxial eccentricity is sufficient to understand element behaviour. This study

is limited to local buckling behaviour and does not consider any other buckling mode or interactions. The numerical results were compared with DSM considering linear interaction equations.

Numerical Modeling and Analysis

General

The numerical analysis was carried out using the computer-aided engineering software ABAQUS. The eccentricities were varied along both symmetric and non-symmetric axis. Initially, eigenvalue buckling analysis was performed on the models to acquire the buckling mode because of which the critical buckling load was obtained. This was followed by non-linear analysis carried out using STATIC RIKS. An imperfection factor of 0.34 times thickness of specimen was used for analysis. The pin-ended boundary condition was modelled by restraining translation degrees of freedom at both end except for one translation degree of freedom axially acting from top of the specimen. The rotation about the longitudinal axis was restrained at both ends. The models were meshed using structured quad elements. The methodology adopted include fixing model dimension, validation, mesh convergence study, followed by a parametric study. At the outset of the numerical study, different parameters were chosen to fix the model dimensions as detailed in Table 1. The eccentric load was varied along both symmetric and non-symmetric axes resulting in eight eccentricities and concentric loading conditions.

Table 1. Parameters incorporated while fixing model dimensions

Parameters	Type finalised
Loading condition	Eccentric and Concentric loading
h/b ratio	1 and 3.05
Buckling initiation	Web and Flange buckling
Length of specimen	Three times largest cross-section dimension
Thickness of specimen	Fixed 1.6 mm – 4 mm (industrial standard)
Element Class	Slender sections

Validation

As a first step, validation of the numerical models was carried out based on inputs from experiments conducted by [1, 2]. On performing a non-linear analysis, all five models predicted the ultimate load within a permissible error of about 3%. The results are compiled and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Validation of numerical model with experimental results

Specimen	$P_{u,exp}$ (kN)	$P_{u,FEM}$ (kN)	Error (%)
P36P0280	55.20	56.83	2.95
P36P0315	52.10	50.85	-2.40
P36P0815	40.90	41.73	2.03
P48P0300	45.20	46.43	2.72
P48P0565	38.60	39.54	2.44

Mesh Convergence Study

The validation of the models was followed by a mesh convergence study. A cross-section of $90 \times 90 \times 1.6$ was selected for the same. The mesh size was varied from 1 to 10 times the model thickness. Considering the mesh convergence, a value of $2t$ was chosen. The results for are tabulated in Table 3. The plot between mesh size and the ratio of critical buckling load to yield load is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. Mesh convergence study

Mesh size $\times t$ (mm)	P_{cr} (kN)	P_{cr}/P_y	Variation (%)
1	28.84	0.173	
2	28.88	0.173	0.15
5	29.02	0.174	0.47
10	29.35	0.176	1.14

Fig. 1. Plot between mesh size and ratio of critical buckling load to yield load

Fig. 2. Mesh convergence study (Abaqus)

Parametric Study

Size Effect

In order to accommodate size effect, two different cross-sections were chosen such that the h/b ratio and flange width-to-thickness ratio remain constant. Accordingly, 90×90×1.6 (PC1) and 120×120×2.13 (PC2) were analysed and the results are displayed in Table 4. The length of the models were set as three times the largest cross-sectional dimension in order to make it undergo local buckling. A yield stress of 350 MPa has been chosen for the models. A plot between the eccentricity and the ratio of ultimate load to yield load is shown in Fig. 3.

Table 4. Size effect for PC1-90×90×1.6

Specimen ID	P_{u-FEM} (kN)	P_{u-FEM}/P_y	Specimen ID	P_{u-FEM} (kN)	P_{u-FEM}/P_y
90×90×1.6-E0	37.66	0.25	120×120×2.13-E0	62.59	0.24
90×90×1.6-E1	29.45	0.20	120×120×2.13-E1	52.21	0.20
90×90×1.6-E2	15.58	0.10	120×120×2.13-E2	28.07	0.11
90×90×1.6-E3	17.78	0.12	120×120×2.13-E3	32.45	0.12
90×90×1.6-E4	46.01	0.31	120×120×2.13-E4	111.93	0.42
90×90×1.6-E5	61.73	0.41	120×120×2.13-E5	125.52	0.47
90×90×1.6-E6	75.32	0.50	120×120×2.13-E6	122.99	0.46
90×90×1.6-E7	30.92	0.21	120×120×2.13-E7	55.16	0.21
90×90×1.6-E8	26.69	0.18	120×120×2.13-E8	48.05	0.18

Fig. 3. Size effect plot for eccentricity along symmetric (x-axis) and non-symmetric (y-axis) axes respectively

Effect of Yield

Effect of yield has been accounted for in this study for the cross-section having h/b ratio 1. The cross-section dimension of the models was set as 90×90×1.6 and two different yield stresses of 266 MPa and 350 MPa were considered. The length of the models was set as three times largest cross-section dimension that is 270 mm. The results are displayed in Table 5. The ratio between ultimate load and yield load has been plotted against the eccentricity as shown in Fig. 4.

Table 5. Effect of yield for 90×90×1.6

Specimen ID	Eccentricity		F _y (MPa)					
	e _x (mm)	e _y (mm)	350			266		
			P _{cr,I-FEM} (kN)	P _{u-FEM} /P _y	P _{u-FEM} (kN)	P _{cr,I-FEM} (kN)	P _{u-FEM} /P _y	P _{u-FEM} (kN)
90×90×1.6-E0	0.00	0.00	28.88	0.25	37.66	27.93	0.29	33.09
90×90×1.6-E1	7.38	0.00	21.98	0.20	29.45	21.27	0.23	26.19
90×90×1.6-E2	38.42	0.00	10.91	0.10	15.58	10.55	0.12	13.79
90×90×1.6-E3	29.64	0.00	12.73	0.12	17.78	12.31	0.14	15.48
90×90×1.6-E4	-5.89	0.00	38.32	0.31	46.01	37.06	0.36	41.44
90×90×1.6-E5	-29.30	0.00	67.69	0.41	61.73	65.47	0.44	49.57
90×90×1.6-E6	-14.69	0.00	68.66	0.50	75.32	66.42	0.58	65.95
90×90×1.6-E7	0.00	-33.82	15.89	0.21	30.92	15.38	0.24	27.56
90×90×1.6-E8	0.00	-50.74	12.76	0.18	26.69	12.35	0.20	22.74

Fig. 4. Effect of yield stress for eccentricity along symmetric and non-symmetric axes respectively

Effect of h/b Ratio

The effect of the ratio of height of the web to the width of the flange (h/b) has been accounted for in this study. Two sets of cross-sections with h/b ratios 1 and 3.05 has been considered. The first set was assigned a cross-section of 90×90×3.95 and the second set of cross-section 90×29.5×1.9 keeping the non-dimensional slenderness value a constant. The yield strength was set as 350 MPa. The length of the models were set as thrice the largest cross-sectional dimension that is 270 mm. The results are displayed in Table 6. The plot between eccentricity and ratio of ultimate load to yield load is shown in Fig. 5. The failure modes of models for the eccentricity E3 is shown in Fig. 6.

Table 6. Effect of h/b ratio

h/b		1		3.05		
Stress ratio	Specimen ID	P _{u-FEM} (kN)	P _{u-FEM} /P _y	Specimen ID	P _{u-FEM} (kN)	P _{u-FEM} /P _y
1.00	90×90×3.95-E0	276.05	0.76	90×29.5×1.9-E0	73.44	0.77
0.50	90×90×3.95-E1	212.04	0.59	90×29.5×1.9-E1	55.84	0.58
-0.08	90×90×3.95-E2	104.77	0.29	90×29.5×1.9-E2	14.59	0.15
0.00	90×90×3.95-E3	122.42	0.34	90×29.5×1.9-E3	21.68	0.23
0.50	90×90×3.95-E4	313.52	0.87	90×29.5×1.9-E4	67.60	0.70
-0.50	90×90×3.95-E5	198.91	0.55	90×29.5×1.9-E5	52.96	0.55
0.00	90×90×3.95-E6	271.06	0.75	90×29.5×1.9-E6	60.26	0.63
0.00	90×90×3.95-E7	152.05	0.42	90×29.5×1.9-E7	43.41	0.45
-0.20	90×90×3.95-E8	121.93	0.34	90×29.5×1.9-E8	39.61	0.41

Fig. 5. Effect of h/b ratio for eccentricity along symmetric and non-symmetric axes respectively

Fig. 6. Failure mode of model 90×90×3.95-E3 and 90×29.5×1.9-E3 respectively

Direct Strength Method (DSM)

The numerical results were compared with DSM making use of linear interaction equations and is displayed in Table 7. The plots between the ratio of ultimate load to yield load for both DSM prediction and FEM results for the two aspect ratios are shown in Fig. 7 for symmetric axis and Fig. 8 for non-symmetric axis.

Table 7. Comparison of FEM and DSM

Sl.No.	Specimen ID	Eccentricity		$P_{u,FEM} / P_y$	$P_{u,DSM} / P_y$
		e_x (mm)	e_y (mm)		
1	90×90×3.95-E0	0.00	0.00	0.762	0.680
2	90×90×3.95-E1	7.20	0.00	0.585	0.390
3	90×90×3.95-E2	37.88	0.00	0.289	0.080
4	90×90×3.95-E3	29.14	0.00	0.338	0.110
5	90×90×3.95-E4	-5.73	0.00	0.870	0.520
6	90×90×3.95-E5	-28.30	0.00	0.550	0.390
7	90×90×3.95-E6	-14.25	0.00	0.750	0.270
8	90×90×3.95-E7	0.00	-32.15	0.420	0.170
9	90×90×3.95-E8	0.00	-48.23	0.340	0.110
10	90×29.5×1.9-E0	0.00	0.00	0.770	0.800
11	90×29.5×1.9-E1	2.09	0.00	0.582	0.504
12	90×29.5×1.9-E2	22.31	0.00	0.152	0.073
13	90×29.5×1.9-E3	13.27	0.00	0.226	0.135
14	90×29.5×1.9-E4	-1.37	0.00	0.705	0.578
15	90×29.5×1.9-E5	-5.17	0.00	0.552	0.289
16	90×29.5×1.9-E6	-3.05	0.00	0.628	0.430
17	90×29.5×1.9-E7	0.00	-25.56	0.453	0.293
18	90×29.5×1.9-E8	0.00	-30.67	0.413	0.248

Fig. 7. Comparison of DSM and FEM for h/b ratio 1 and 3.05 respectively along symmetric axis

Different boundary conditions were considered in the Finite Strip Method software GBTUL in order to check for the deviation of DSM values from FEM results. The deviation from numerical results obtained from ABAQUS was found to be minimum when compared to DSM in case of $P_{cr,l}$ values obtained from the signature curve.

Results and Discussions

The results obtained from Table 4 and Fig. 3 help in concluding that size effect is negligible on the ultimate load to yield load ratio for plain channel subjected to eccentric loading when h/b ratio and flange width-to-thickness ratio is kept constant. The effect of yield stress on the ultimate load to yield load ratio for an eccentrically loaded plain channel can be ignored when the h/b ratio remains a constant which is concluded from Table 5 and Fig. 4. On analysing the effect of aspect ratio on ultimate load to yield load ratio for plain channels under eccentric loading conditions, the following points were observed:

- It was found that the ratio of ultimate load to yield load was varying at the same stress ratio under each eccentricity

for both the cross-sections for the same non-dimensional slenderness ratio. Hence this parameter cannot be neglected.

- As the eccentricity approaches the web element, the cross-section with h/b ratio 3.05 has lower ratio of ultimate load to yield load at each stress ratio as compared to the h/b ratio 1. This is because the element slenderness ratio for web (web height-to-thickness ratio) is more for the former cross-section thus making it slenderer. The slenderness of the element is inversely proportional to the load carrying capacity.
- As the eccentricity approaches the flange element, the cross-section with h/b ratio 1 has lower ratio of ultimate load to yield load as compared to the h/b ratio 3.05. This is because the flange element slenderness ratio (flange width-to-thickness ratio) is more for the former cross-section thus making it slenderer which reduces its load carrying capacity.
- The effect of ultimate load to yield load ratio between the h/b ratios 1 and 3.05 was observed to be decreasing when the eccentricity is approaching to zero along both the symmetric and non-symmetric axis.

The DSM predictions were compared with FEM results for both aspect ratios as displayed in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The following observations were made:

- The DSM result was found to be unconservative for the aspect ratio of 3.05 as compared to the aspect ratio of 1 under concentric loading condition of plain channel for the same non-dimensional slenderness ratio as concluded by [3]
- Forth eccentric loading condition, in general, it was observed that the DSM predictions gave overconservative results for both the aspect ratios.

Fig. 8. Comparison of DSM and FEM for h/b ratio 1 and 3.05 respectively along non-symmetric axis

Conclusions

A systematic numerical analysis was carried out to examine the influence of the aspect ratio of the plain channel subjected to uniaxial eccentric loading. The results obtained aid in design of plain channel sections and can be used to understand the local buckling behaviour of beam-column with varying elemental stress distribution. Two different aspect ratios were considered for the same. The size effect and the effect of yield stresses were also included in the study. The eccentric load was varied along both symmetric and non-symmetric axes. The results confirmed that both the element stress ratio and element slenderness ratio is having an effect on the load carrying capacity of an eccentrically load plain channel stub column. The numerical results were compared with DSM predictions. It was observed that for plain channel subjected to eccentric loading under pin-ended support condition the results obtained for both the aspect ratios were found to be overconservative. The models were analysed by considering two aspect ratios keeping the non-dimensional slenderness ratio as a constant. The results showed variations indicating that h/b ratio is not the only governing factor, but the results are also governed by stress ratio and the element slenderness ratio for predicting the capacity of eccentrically loaded beam-column.

References

1. Young B and Rasmussen KJR (1998), “Tests of fixed-ended plain channel columns”, Journal of Structural Engineering, 124:131–139.
2. Young B and Rasmussen KJR (1999), “Behaviour of cold-formed singly symmetric columns”, Thin Walled

Structures, 22:83-102

3. Young B Ben and Rasmussen KJR (1999), "Shift of effective centroid of channel columns", *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 125:524–531.
4. Young B (2006), "Local buckling and shift of effective centroid of slender sections"
5. Rao KS (1998), (PhD Thesis), "Coupled local and torsional-flexural buckling of cold-formed steel members"
6. Beulah Gnana Ananthi G, Samuel Knight GM, Iyer NR, Marimuthu V (2012), "Behaviour of cold-formed plain channels under compression", *Journal of Structural Engineering (India)*, 39:355–362
7. Nivethitha AP, Vani G, Jayabalan P (2014), "Numerical analysis of eccentrically loaded cold-formed plain channel columns", *Journal of Structures*, 2014:1–10.
8. Zain MRM, Wee LS, Rosli MIF, Hamid HA (2010), "Numerical investigation of cold-formed steel channel columns subjected to axial thrust", *CSSR 2010 - 2010 International Conference on Science and Social Research*, 292–297.
9. Ye J, Hajirasouliha I, Becque J (2018), "Experimental investigation of local-flexural interactive buckling of cold-formed steel channel columns", *Thin Walled Structures*, 125:245–258.
10. Schafer BW (2008), "Review: The Direct Strength Method of cold-formed steel member design", *Journal of Construction Steel Research*, 64:766–778.
11. Kumar MVA, Kalyanaraman V (2010), "Evaluation of Direct Strength Method for CFS compression members without stiffeners", *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 136:879–885.
12. Vijayavengadesh Kumar J, Arul Jayachandran S (2016), "Experimental investigation and evaluation of Direct Strength Method on beam-column behavior of uprights", *Thin-Walled Structures*, 102:165–179.
13. Rajkannu JS, Jayachandran SA (2022), "Experimental evaluation of DSM beam-column strength of cold-formed steel members under uniaxial eccentric compression", *Thin-Walled Structures*, 174.
14. Mahar AM, Jayachandran SA, Mahendran M (2021) Direct Strength Method for cold-formed steel unlippped channel columns subject to local buckling. *International Journal of Steel Structures* 21:1977–1987.